
Enriching the School Environment in Context of IKS With Reference To Academic Achievement of the Adolescents

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ABSTRACT

Enriching the school environment through the integration of Indigenous Knowledge system (IKS) can positively impact the academic achievement of adolescents. NEP-2020 aims to revitalize India's education system by integrating and promoting traditional Indian knowledge, a huge repository encompassing science, engineering, medical agriculture, mathematics and philosophy by connecting the students with their own cultural heritage. Strategies include collaborating with local communities, using culturally responsive teaching methods, and integrating IKS into various subjects. The paper analyzes the potential impact, challenges, and opportunities of NEP 2020 on the Indian knowledge system. It explores how traditional knowledge systems can be blended with modern educational practices to enrich the school environment, to ameliorate the academic achievement of the adolescents for a holistic learning environment.

Introduction:

The Modern Indian Education System Is A Combination Of Traditional Values And Contemporary Learning Frameworks. Ethics And Value-Based Education Were Fundamental To The

Ancient Indian Education System. Key Values Like Self-Reliance, Empathy, Creativity, And Integrity Were Central To Ancient Indian Society And Remain Relevant Today. The Indian Knowledge Systems (Iks) Initiative Aims To Encourage And Support Research That Addresses Into Educational Platforms, With A Focus On Improving The Quality Of Classroom Teaching Through Teacher Training And Mentoring Development Programmes. This Initiative Is Rooted In The Rich Tradition Of Vedic Literature, Including The Vedas And Upanishads. Iks Is Currently Being Integrated To National Education Policy Proposed Various Reforms Across Several Areas Of Education, Skill Development, And Assessments Systems. Recognizing India's Linguistic Diversity, It Also Emphasizes The Importance Of Mother-Tongue-Based Multilingual Education In The Early Years. Furthermore, The Evaluation Of Education In Ancient India Went Beyond Simply Grading Theoretical Knowledge; Students Were Assessed On Their Acquired Skills And Their Ability To Apply Practical Knowledge To Real-Life Situations..

The Government Of India Has Prioritized The Promotion Of Indian Language And The Integration Of Indian Knowledge System Into Mainstream Education. This Initiative Aims To Preserve And Propagate India's Rich Linguistic And Intellectual Heritage, While Fostering An Inclusive And Multilingual Learning Environment. Through Curriculum Reforms, Digital Platforms, And Institutional Support, The Policy Also Aims To Alleviate The Immense Pressure On Students And Families Caused By High Stakes Exams, Particularly Board Examinations.

School Environment:

Environmental Factors, Including A Student's Home Environment And Peer Group, Significantly Impact Academic Performance. High Achieving Peers Can Positively Influence A Student, While Institutional Factors Like The Quality Of Instruction And Available School Resources Are Also Crucial. A Supportive School Environment Fosters Student Autonomy, Motivation, And Learning Habits, And This Development Is Further Shaped By Parenting Styles And The Overall School Environment.

The School Environment Is Said As The "The Heart And Soul Of The School", Influence The Commitment Of The Students, Teachers And Administrators. Various Pens Defined It As The School's Unwritten Personality And Atmosphere, Encompassing Norms. A Healthy School Climate Is Described As A Collective Experience That Involves Students, Parents, Teachers, And Staff, Shaped By Rules, Goals, Interactions, Teaching Methods, And Institutional Structures. This Environment Aims To Ensure The Social, Emotional, And Physical Safety Of Students. Furthermore, A Positive School Environment Acts As A Protective Barrier Against Mental Health Issues And Improves Academic Outcomes,

Particularly For Marginalized Students, By Narrowing Achievement Gapes And Promoting Educational Equality. It Emphasizes That, School Environment Is Not About Administrative Or Physical Attributes Like Teacher Salaries Or Resources, But Rather The Interpersonal Interactions, Affecting Psychological Adjustment, Mental Health, Self-Esteem, And Even Influencing Bullying , Aggressive Behavior, Delinquency And Substance Use.

A Positive Perception Of The School Environment Is Directly Linked To Academic Success And Helps To Prevent Negative Outcomes Like Harmful Behavior And Violence Within The School.

Academic Achievement:

Academic Achievement Refers To A Student's Performance In Educational Settings, Typically Measured Through Grades, Tests And Other Assessments, A Student's Motivation And Engagement With Learning Materials And Activities Significantly Influence Their Academic Success. It Also Includes Learning Ability, Knowledge Acquisition, Grade Attainment, And Improved Attendance Among School Going Adolescents. Positive Teacher Student Relationships And Constructive Peer Interactions Are Crucial For Fostering Better Academic Outcomes. Active Parental Involvement And Support From Home Play A Vital Role In Influencing A Student's Academic Achievements. The Most Important Of All Is The Student Abilities, Preferred Learning Styles, And Personal Characteristics To Their Overall Academic Performance.

Research Focus:

The Study Aims To Access The School Environment By Incorporating Our Traditional Knowledge And Connect Their Learning And Insert It Into Our Curriculum Especially In The Context Of Indigenous Knowledge Systems. This Approach Can Be Useful For The Adolescents To Connect Them To Their Own Cultural Heritage, Making Education More Meaningful And Relevant For Adolescents.

Objectives:

The Article Aims To Acknowledge The Advantages And Challenges Of Integration Of Indigenous Knowledge Systems (Iks) In Education, Including Its Challenges And The Role Of Teacher Training, To Fulfill Two Main Goals, As Well As To Create A

It Aims To Understand The Advantages Of Integrating Iks Into Education, Which Can Lead To A More Comprehensive And Culturally Appropriate Learning Environment For Students. It Also Investigates Potential Obstacles To Integrating Iks Into School Curricula.

It Pinpoints The Specific Aspects Of Teacher Training Programs That Need Enhancement To Effectively Embed Iks Into Their Teaching Practices.

Present Status Of Indian Education System:

It Emphasizes The Digital Education System As A Key Enabler Of Accessibility And Innovation. The National Educational Policy (Nep) 2020 Proposes Reforms In Early Childhood Education, Skill Development, And Assessment System Highlighting The Importance Of Mother-Tongue-Based Multilingual Education In Early Years. It Also Addresses The Significant Mismatch Between Skills Taught In Institutions And Those Required By The Job Market, Advocating For Vocational Education And Integrating Skills Training Into The School Curriculum To Reduce Pressure From Board Examination Requirements By Focusing On Vocational Education And Integrating Skills Training Into The School Curriculum To Reduce Pressure From Board Examinations On Student And Families.

Enriching The School Environment In Context Of Indigenous Knowledge Systems (Iks) Can Significantly Boost The Academic Achievement Of The Adolescents. It Involves Creating A Supporting And Inclusive And Inclusive Atmosphere That Values Students' Cultural Backgrounds And Promotes Their Over-All Well-Being. In Context Of Iks, Enriching The School Environment Could Mean Incorporating Traditional Knowledge And Practices Into The Curriculum. This Approach Can Help Adolescents To Connect Their Learning To Their Cultural Heritage, Making Education More Meaningful And Relevant.

“In Raipur, 61 Government Schools Operating Since Before Independence Will Now Be Developed As Heritage Schools. This Will Give Children An Opportunity To Learn About The Historical And Cultural Significance Of Their School, As Well As Their Heritage And Ancestors. These Schools Will Teach About The Revolutionaries From Before Independence. The Schools Will Also Be Named After Them. This Scheme Will Help Students Connect With Their Roots And Understand The Importance Of Their Heritage And History. It Could Also Promote Raipur As A Tourist Destination. In The Process Of Developing The 61 Schools Into Heritage Schools, The Stories Of These Revolutionaries Will Be Digitally Described. Additionally, Any Shortcomings In These Schools Will Be Addressed. This Includes Fulfilling All Types Of Needs Such As School Painting, And Shortage Of Teachers.”

Strategies To Enrich The School Environment:

It Is A Matter Of Concern To Consider Our Deep-Rooted Traditions Of Gurukul System Into Modern Education To Achieve A Holistic And Long-Term Vision For India's Future .It Had Been

Enriched With All-Round Development, Including Character Building And Practical Skills, Long Before Modern Education Emphasized These Aspects. Essentially It Advocates For A Balanced Approach To Education That Combines Traditional Wisdom With Contemporary Advancements For The Betterment Of Future Generations And The Nation's Progress.

1. Cultural Integration
2. Community Engagement
3. Supportive Climate

Cultural Integration:

It Refers To The Process Of Blending Different Cultural Practices, Values And Traditions To Create A Cohesive And Inclusive Environment. In Context Of Education, Cultural Integration Can Enrich Learning Experiences By Connecting Students' Cultural Backgrounds To The Curriculum.

1. Preservation Of Languages: Schools In Some Regions Integrate Local Languages And Cultural Stories Into Curricula, Enhancing Students' Connection To Learning.
2. Community Based Project: Projects That Involve Local Communities And Iks Have Led To Increased Student Engagement And Relevance Of Learning.
3. Cultural Festivals And Events: Schools Celebrating Local Cultural Festivals And Events To Integrate Iks Into The School Environment. Participants Must Receive Pre-Departure Orientation And Cultural Competency Training To Approach The Experience With Respect, Openness, And Humility.
4. Holistic Understanding: Blending Iks With Formal Education Fosters A More Holistic Understanding Of Subjects Including Moral, Ethical And Spiritual Dimensions.

Benefits Of Cultural Integration:

1. Enhances Relevance: Integration With Education Makes It More Relevant And Meaningful To The Students From Diverse Cultural Backgrounds.
2. Increased Engagement: Students Are More Likely To Engage With Learning Materials That Reflect Their Cultural Heritage And Potentially Academic Achievements,
3. Promote Inclusivity: Fosters An Inclusive Environment, Where Diverse Cultures Are Valued And Respected.

Challenges For Implementation:

Balancing Curriculum Requirements: Introducing Iks At Each And Every Levels From Primary To Higher Education, In Order To A Holistic Development Of Pupils And Integration Meets Curriculum Requirements While Maintaining Cultural Relevance.

Teacher Training: Providing Teachers With Training To Effectively Integrate Iks Into Their Teaching Practices.

Community Partnership: Building Strong Partnerships With Local Communities To Support Iks Integration.

Respect And Representation: Ensuring Accurate Representation And Respect For Diverse Cultures In Educational Materials.

Community Engagement:

Community engagement in school environment, especially in context of Indigenous Knowledge system

Language integration:

To Promote classical languages like Sanskrit, Pali and Prakrit along with contemporary languages, involvement of community elders to teach local languages alongside mainstream subjects have seen increased student engagement.

Community based Projects: Projects like traditional crafts, farming practices, or local storytelling integrated into curricula have enhanced relevance and engagement.

Cultural events and celebrations: Schools celebrating local festivals or cultural events with community involvement have fostered stronger connections between students, cultural heritage and learning.

Strategies for Community Engagement:

Collaborate with Local Elders: To involve community elders in curriculum development or classroom activities to integrate IKS.

Community based Learning: Encourage learning experiences that take place within the community, leveraging local knowledge and practices.

Parental Involvement: Engage parents and community members in supporting students' learning, bridging school and community.

Encourage Shared learning: Facilitate shared learning experiences between students, teachers and community members.

Benefits:

Improved Engagement: Students may show improved engagement and academic performance when learning is connected to their cultural context.

Contextualized Learning: IKS integration through community engagement can make learning more contextualized and meaningful.

Challenges and Solutions:

Building Relationships: Challenges of building trust with communities and it can be solved by consistent communication and involvement of community leaders transparency, and active listening are needful for it.

Balancing Curriculum: Challenge of integrating (IKS) without compromising curriculum standards. It can be come to a solution by collaborative curriculum planning with community input.

Resource Limitations: This problem could be overcome by utilizing the strength and assets of individuals, organizations, and groups within a community to achieve a shared goal. This involves building relationships, sharing expertise and resources, and working collaboratively to address community needs and challenges.

Supportive Climate: Some key aspects of supportive climate with IKS are:

Cultural Relevance: Integrating IKS creates a culturally relevant learning environment, making education more meaningful for adolescents.

Inclusivity and Respect: Fosters inclusivity and respect for diverse cultural backgrounds, enhancing students sense of belonging.

Engagement and Motivation: Supports engagement and motivation by connecting learning to students' cultural contexts.

Impact on academic achievement:

Enhanced engagement: Students are more likely to engage academically when learning connects to their cultural heritage.

Holistic learning Experiences: Blending IKS with formal education leads to a more holistic learning experience.

Cultural pride and Identity: Supports cultural pride and identity, potentially boosting academic confidence.

Strategies for creating a supporting climate with IKS:

Community Involvement: Engage local communities and elders in school activities and curriculum development.

Culturally Responsive Teaching: It encourages teaching practices that respect and incorporate students' cultural backgrounds.

Inclusive Environment: Foster an inclusive school environment valuing diverse

Challenge and Strategies for implementation:

Teacher Preparedness: Ensuring teachers are prepared to integrate IKS it is needful to provide them with professional development and resources.

Community Engagement: Building strong community partnerships regular communication and involvement of community leaders.

GOVERNMENT POLICIES:

- Government policies and initiatives with funding are much needful to address the challenges and priorities of IKS in mainstream of education.
- Increase of Government spending on Education.
- Strengthen Teacher Training.
- Accelerate the implementation of NEP 2020
- Develop a Comprehensive Framework.
- National Program on Technology Enhanced learning.
- Samagra Shikha Abhiyana.

- Pragyata (Plan, Review, Arrange, Guide, Yak, Assign, Track, and Appreciate).

There is also needful of evidence based planning like:

- Capacity Building.
- Localized strategies.
- Monitoring and Evaluation.
- Comprehensive Training Programmes.
- Collaborative Planning.
- Regular Sharing of best practices

Conclusion:

Enriching the Indian knowledge system (IKS) into modern higher education offers a transformative approach to developing skillful, responsible, and resilient individuals, by emphasizing interdisciplinary learning, ethical values, mindfulness, environmental awareness, and creative expressions. It equips students to navigate contemporary challenges with a strong sense of cultural identity and ethical grounding. Educational institutions striving to create more holistic school environments can significantly benefit from incorporating IKS into curricula, promising to develop students who are not only knowledgeable but also compassionate, culturally rooted to the interconnected world. These insights call upon policymakers and educators to explore the potentiality of IKS to enrich modern education. This integrated approach combines individualized learning with modern technologies and incorporates ancient Indian knowledge, can help students to understand India's intellectual heritage and provide solutions to their problems. Ultimately, closing the gap between traditional and modern approaches aims to produce a generation of competent professionals who can contribute to a sustainable and just global society.

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